

English with Brazilian beat: Brazilian English word stress and vowel reduction

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Abstract

This study examined vowel reduction as a correlate for word stress assignment in native (L1) and non-native (L2) speakers of American English (AE) through a word reading task. In trisyllabic words, L1 speakers reduced unstressed vowels more in duration than L2 speakers, confirming predictions about temporal vowel reduction. While F0 pitch peaks and vowel quality did not differ significantly between groups, intensity and spectral characteristics of English reduced vowels revealed key distinctions. Both groups used greater intensity for stressed vowels, suggesting that mean intensity is a stress marker. However, L2 speakers produced generally higher mean intensities on stressed vowels, indicating a reliance on non-native phonetic correlates to approximate native-like stress patterns. Spectral analyses showed that L2 speakers did not reduce vowels as narrowly in the F1-F2 space as L1 speakers, likely due to the influence of their native language (Brazilian Portuguese), which does not present spectral reduction. This broader spectral realization suggests a merged L1-L2 acoustic system in bilinguals, where reduced vowels may overlap with full vowel categories. These findings support the view that L2 speakers can achieve phonological targets using different acoustic strategies and highlight intensity and spectral correlates as strong acoustic correlates for word stress, rather than F0, in signaling stress in both L1 and L2 AE productions.

Index Terms: Acoustic Phonetics, Word Stress, American English L2, Brazilian Portuguese L1

1. Introduction

Word stress in American English (AE) is marked by both segmental and suprasegmental correlates, with vowel quality, duration, intensity, and pitch movement contributing to the perception and production of stress [1], [2], [3], [4]. Stressed vowels are typically longer, louder, and more spectrally distinct than unstressed vowels, which tend to be centralized, often realized as Schwa. Pitch peaks commonly align with stressed syllables, especially in isolated or focused contexts. Among these correlates, vowel quality has been shown to be the most influential for word recognition, surpassing suprasegmental features like F0 pitch movement.

In Brazilian Portuguese (BP), F0 pitch peaks and falls on the most prominent syllable, and duration is considered the primary correlate of stress in BP, with unstressed vowels being significantly shorter than stressed ones, though differences are not as extreme as in English [5], [6]. Unstressed vowels in BP retain their spectral properties, lacking the centralization found

in AE [7]. F0 contours in BP differ from AE, typically featuring a plateau on the stressed syllable followed by a steep fall [8], [9].

Cross-linguistic differences in vowel inventories and stress correlates can lead to merged phonetic categories in bilingual speakers. For instance, BP speakers may merge AE vowels /i/ and /ɪ/ categories, resulting in lexical ambiguity and increased competition during word retrieval [10]. These differences emphasize the importance of examining how L1 phonological systems influence L2 stress perception and production.

In the present Experiment, we applied a word reading task to test the hypothesis that the reduced versus full vowel categories in native English are not contrastive in word stress in BP English word productions.

2. Methods

This study involved two groups of participants: ten native monolingual speakers of American English and ten Brazilian speakers of English as a second language, equally divided by gender. The American participants ranged in age from 19 to 48 (mean age: 25.6), while the Brazilian participants were aged 21 to 44 (mean age: 30). All participants were selected after completing a linguistic background questionnaire. To ensure linguistic comparability, Brazilian participants were required to report their English proficiency scores and take the X_Lex 2.05 vocabulary test [11], with only those scoring above 3,500 points (out of 5,000) included, indicating upper-intermediate to advanced proficiency. All participants had normal or corrected vision and no reported hearing issues. Participation was compensated, although some volunteered without payment.

The experiment used a set of 360 three-syllable English words, stressed on either the first or second syllable (half of the words for each stress pattern) extracted from a bilingual English-Portuguese Corpus [12]. Example: ALphabet vs. forBIDden. The full set of words used as stimuli is available in [13].

Participants were seated in a booth, approximately 60 cm from a computer screen, and engaged in a word reading task using E-Prime 2.0 software. Words were displayed individually and in isolation in black Arial font, preceded by a fixation cross, and presented for 1000 ms. Participants had 3000 ms to pronounce each word, which was recorded using a high-quality microphone. The experiment was divided into four blocks and preceded by a training phase with 20 non-experimental words.

Speech responses were recorded within a 4.5-second window and processed using Praat [14] scripts for segmentation,

labeling, and phonological transcription¹. The automated transcription was checked by the first author of this paper and by another phonetician, Dr. Judith Varkevisser. Ambiguous transcriptions were discarded, thus, nine words were excluded from the final analysis to ensure data reliability.

3. Results

Participants produced 360 trisyllabic words each, totaling 7,200 words, with stress distributed across the first and second syllables. After excluding 16 words due to transcription ambiguities, 6,880 word tokens were analyzed, considering only the first and second syllables to avoid final lengthening effects [15, 16].

3.1 Duration of American English Full and Reduced Vowels as produced by L1 and L2 speakers

Because BP typically features spectrally full vowels regardless of stress and exhibits minimal durational contrast between stressed and unstressed vowels, we hypothesized that BP speakers would demonstrate a smaller duration ratio between reduced and full vowels compared to native English speakers. In the English target words, full vowels appeared only in stressed syllables, while reduced vowels were confined to unstressed positions. As anticipated, native AE speakers exhibited a larger contrast in vowel duration between full and reduced vowels compared to BP speakers, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: *Native and non-native American English vowel duration means.*

	Full vowels	Reduced vowels	Ratio full/reduced vowels
AE L1	109 (33)	65 (32)	1.68
AE L2	113 (39)	78 (38)	1.43

Note. AE L1 = native speakers of American English; AE L2 = American English L2 produced by Brazilians (BP as L1). Durations in milliseconds and standard deviations in parentheses.

To account for individual differences in speech rate, vowel durations were z-normalized per speaker, with scores ranging from -3 to 7; six outliers falling outside the -2 to 6 range were excluded, leaving 11,459 vowel tokens for analysis. A Multiple Regression Analysis with fixed factors was performed in R [17] in order to investigate how Language Group (American English as L1 or L2) and Vowel Quantity (full or reduced vowels) affect vowel duration production in American English as produced by L1 and L2 speakers.

The model revealed a significant main effect of Language Group (Estimate = 0.22, SE = 0.07, $t = 3.07$, $p = .02$), indicating that L2 speakers produced longer vowels than L1 speakers. Vowel Quantity also showed a significant main effect (Estimate = -1.16, SE = 0.16, $t = -7.23$, $p < .01$), confirming that stressed full vowels were longer than unstressed reduced vowels. Additionally, the interaction between Language Group and Vowel Quantity was significant (Estimate = 0.22, SE = 0.10, t

= 2.16, $p = .03$), suggesting that the contrast in vowel duration between full and reduced vowels varied depending on the speaker's language background. This finding highlights that the production of vowel contrasts in English is influenced by the speaker's linguistic background, with non-native speakers showing a less pronounced contrast.

To find out whether Brazilians and Americans showed a similar duration reduction to English vowels, a closer look is needed at the reduced vowel durations. The reduced vowels present in this dataset are the mid-central vowel (also known as Schwa, phonetic symbol /ə/), and the near-close front unrounded vowel (phonetic symbol /ɪ/), which were produced either on the first or second syllables of the trisyllabic words. Altogether, 5,673 reduced vowels were available in our dataset. After outliers (with raw durations inferior to -1.5 and superior to 2.5 Z-scores) were excluded, a total of 5,535 items remained for analysis.

Table 2: *Duration of American English reduced vowels*

Vowel	AE L1	AE L2
/ə/	68 (34)	82 (37)
/ɪ/	61 (25)	69 (31)

Note. Idem Table 1

The mean durations of reduced vowels suggest that non-native speakers produce longer vowels than native speakers of American English. To investigate whether the degree of vocalic reduction differs between native and non-native English speakers, two separate Multiple Regression Analyses were conducted in R [17]: one for Schwa vowels and another for Near-close front unrounded vowels. The dependent variable was the z-score of vowel duration, and Language Group (L1 vs. L2 English) served as the independent variable. After excluding outliers, 3,474 Schwa tokens and 2,040 /ɪ/ vowel tokens were included in the statistical analysis.

The model ran on z-normalized duration values of Schwa vowels revealed a significant intercept (Estimate = -119.76, SE = 0.12, $t = 49.68$, $p < .01$), establishing the baseline duration. Language Group showed a significant main effect (Estimate = 0.35, SE = 0.08, $t = 40.58$, $p < .01$), indicating that Schwa vowels were produced with longer durations by L2 speakers compared to L1 speakers. The model ran on z-normalized duration values of Near-close front unrounded vowels showed the intercept was significant (Estimate = -135.72, SE = 0.12, $t = -11.14$, $p < .01$), establishing the baseline duration. Language Group showed a significant main effect (Estimate = 0.29, SE = 0.08, $t = 3.78$, $p < .01$), indicating that L2 speakers produced this vowel with longer durations than L1 speakers do. Overall, the results revealed that Brazilian speakers exhibited significantly longer durations in reduced vowels than American speakers do, thus, showing that language background significantly influences the extent of temporal vowel reduction in English.

3.2 Spectra of American English Full and Reduced Vowels as produced by American and Brazilian speakers

¹ These scripts were created by Eng. Jos Pacilly (Leiden University Centre for Linguistics) and adapted by the first author of this paper.

Vowel spectra are primarily defined by two acoustic properties: the first formant (F1), which reflects vowel height (close vs. open), and the second formant (F2), which corresponds to vowel frontness (front vs. back) and lip rounding. In this study, F1 and F2 were measured at the temporal midpoint of each vowel. They were converted from Hertz to Barks to account for perceptual scaling [18, 19]. To control for anatomical differences in vocal tract size, z-normalization was applied per speaker across the vowel set. A total of 2,073 tokens were primarily considered. After outliers were excluded (F1[>-1.5. 3.5<]; F2[>-2. 3<] , in Barks), 2,051 tokens remained for analysis.

This part of the study aimed to determine whether Brazilian speakers reduce vowels spectrally in unstressed syllables similarly to native speakers. The first comparison was made between the Near-close front unrounded vowel and its closest full vowel counterpart, the high front vowel, which exists in both English and Portuguese. Data is shown on Table 3.

Table 3: *English High Front vowel and Near-close front unrounded vowel productions by Language*

Vowels	AmE-L1		AmE-L2	
	F1	F2	F1	F2
i	4.07	12.84	3.29	13.63
ɪ	4.34	12.24	3.91	12.85

Note. First and second formant values (F1, F2) measured at the center of the vowels and scaled from Hertz into Barks.

Spectral data showed that L2 speakers produced distinct categories for short and high front vowels, but both were higher and more fronted than those produced by L1 speakers. Notably, the proximity between the L2 short vowel and the L1 high front vowel in the acoustic space suggests that these categories may not be fully differentiated in the vowel system of Brazilian speakers of English. A multivariate multiple regression analysis was conducted to examine the influence of Language Group (L1 vs. L2 English) on the first (F1) and second (F2) formant frequencies of Near-close front unrounded vowels and High Front vowels. For the F1 response, the intercept was significant (Estimate = -0.42, SE = 0.16, t = -2.53, p = .01), indicating a reliable baseline value. However, Language Group did not significantly affect F1 values (Estimate = -0.08, SE = 0.09, t = -0.85, p = .39), suggesting no meaningful difference in vowel height between native and non-native speakers. For the F2 response, the intercept was also significant (Estimate = 0.78, SE = 0.11, t = 6.94, p < .01), establishing a consistent baseline for vowel frontness. Language Group again showed no significant effect on F2 values (Estimate = 0.00, SE = 0.06, t = 0.08, p = .93), indicating that the place of articulation for these vowels did not differ substantially between L1 and L2 speakers. These results suggest that, acoustically, native and non-native speakers produce these vowel types with similar spectral properties.

Subsequently, we analyzed the production of Open-Mid Back vowel in relation to the Mid Central vowel.

Table 4: *F1 and F2 values in Barks of mid-central and open-mid back English vowels as produced by L1 and L2 English speakers*

	AE L1	AE L2
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Vowels	F1	F2	F1	F2
ə	4.74	11.23	4.62	11.14
ʌ	5.23	11.12	4.43	11.27

Note. First and second formant values (F1, F2) measured at the center of the vowels and scaled from Hertz into Barks.

According to Table 4, the spectral characteristics of English Mid and Back vowels, measured through F1 and F2 values in Bark, differ notably between native and non-native speakers. Specifically, the F1 values for /ə/ and /ʌ/ produced by L2 speakers were nearly identical and generally higher than those produced by native speakers, aligning more closely with the Schwa category in L1 English. To further investigate these patterns, a statistical comparison was conducted between the Schwa and one of its closest neighbor in the vowel space, the open-mid back vowel /ʌ/. From an initial dataset of 7,949 tokens, 7,837 remained after excluding outliers based on Bark-scaled F1 and F2 thresholds. Separate multiple regression analyses were performed for L1 and L2 English groups to assess the influence of vowel quality on spectral variation.

A multiple regression analysis was conducted to compare the first (F1) and second (F2) formant frequencies between Schwa (mid central vowel) and the Open-Mid Back vowel as produced by native English speakers. For the F1 response, the intercept was significant (Estimate = 0.64, SE = 0.15, t = 4.22, p < .01), and Vowel Quality showed a significant main effect (Estimate = -0.78, SE = 0.16, t = -4.90, p < .01). This indicates that Schwa vowels were produced with lower F1 values than Open-Mid Back vowels, reflecting a higher tongue position for Schwa. For the F2 response, the intercept was not significant (Estimate = 0.10, SE = 0.17, t = 0.58, p = .56), and Vowel Quality did not show a significant effect (Estimate = -0.18, SE = 0.17, t = -1.01, p = .31). These results suggest that the front-back tongue position (as reflected in F2) did not differ significantly between the two vowel types in native English productions. Overall, the analysis confirms a spectral distinction in vowel height but not in vowel frontness between Schwa and the Open-Mid Back vowel.

Another multiple regression analysis was conducted to compare the first (F1) and second (F2) formant frequencies between Schwa and Open-Mid Back vowels as produced by English L2 speakers. For the F1 response, neither the intercept (Estimate = 0.06, SE = 0.14, t = 0.44, p = .66) nor the main effect of Vowel Quality (Estimate = -0.07, SE = 0.15, t = -0.47, p = .64) reached statistical significance. This indicates that there was no meaningful difference in vowel height between the two vowel types in L2 productions. Similarly, for the F2 response, the intercept was not significant (Estimate = 0.02, SE = 0.15, t = 0.13, p = .10), and Vowel Quality showed no significant effect (Estimate = 0.04, SE = 0.16, t = 0.25, p = .80). These results suggest that L2 speakers did not produce a clear spectral distinction in either height or frontness between Schwa and the Open-Mid Back vowel, indicating a potential overlap or lack of differentiation in their vowel system.

The comparison between native (L1) and non-native (L2) English speakers' productions of Schwa and Open-Mid Back vowels reveals a clear contrast in spectral differentiation. Among L1 speakers, the F1 values showed a significant

difference between the two vowel types, indicating a distinct contrast in vowel height, with Schwa being produced higher than the Open-Mid Back vowel. In contrast, L2 speakers did not exhibit significant differences in either F1 or F2 values, suggesting that they do not reliably distinguish these vowels acoustically. This lack of spectral separation in L2 productions points to a reduced phonological contrast and a possible merging of vowel categories in unstressed syllables.

3.3 Pitch movement in full and reduced vowels of native and non-native American English

The F0 peaks of full and reduced vowels were measured at the time points of 25% duration, 50% duration, and 75% duration in order to reproduce the F0 movement produced on each vowel [19, 20]. A multivariate multiple regression analysis was conducted on 7,974 z-normalized F0 values (converted from Hertz to Semitones) to examine the effects of Language Group (L1 vs. L2 English) and Vowel Quality (full vs. reduced vowels) on mean pitch F0 measured at 25%, 50%, and 75% of vowel duration.

For the F0 at 25%, the intercept was significant (Estimate = 0.165, SE = 0.004, $t = 43.36$, $p < .01$), but neither Language Group (Estimate = 0.002, SE = 0.005, $t = 0.36$, $p = .72$) nor Vowel Quality (Estimate = -0.004, SE = 0.006, $t = -0.73$, $p = .47$) showed significant effects. The interaction between Language Group and Vowel Quality was also non-significant (Estimate = 0.007, SE = 0.008, $t = 0.96$, $p = .34$), indicating that pitch peak differences at this point were not influenced by language background or vowel type. For the F0 peak at 50%, the intercept was not significant (Estimate = -0.016, SE = 0.014, $t = -1.15$, $p = .25$), and neither Language Group (Estimate = 0.022, SE = 0.019, $t = 1.18$, $p = .24$) nor Vowel Quality (Estimate = -0.014, SE = 0.020, $t = -0.71$, $p = .48$) reached significance. Similarly, at 75% of vowel duration, the intercept approached significance (Estimate = -0.039, SE = 0.021, $t = -1.84$, $p = .07$), but Language Group (Estimate = 0.027, SE = 0.030, $t = 0.92$, $p = .36$) and Vowel Quality (Estimate = -0.018, SE = 0.030, $t = -0.60$, $p = .55$) remained non-significant. Across all three time points, the results suggest that pitch peak values were not reliably affected by either language background or vowel type.

3.4 Intensity of full and reduced vowels of American English as L1 and as L2

The mean intensity of full and reduced vowels in American English was analyzed across native (L1) and Brazilian (L2) speakers. After excluding outliers below 40 dB and above 90 dB, 11,300 data points were retained. A subsequent linear regression analysis was performed on 7,605 z-normalized intensity values within speakers, with Language Group and Vowel Quality as fixed factors. Results showed that full vowels were consistently produced with greater intensity than reduced vowels in both language groups.

A linear regression analysis was conducted on z-score mean intensity values to examine the effects of Language Group (L1 vs. L2 English) and Vowel Quality (full vs. reduced vowels) on vowel intensity. The intercept was highly significant (Estimate = 59.29, SE = 0.19, $t = 312.08$, $p < .01$), establishing the baseline intensity level. Language Group showed a significant main effect (Estimate = 3.03, SE = 0.34, $t = 9.02$, $p < .01$), indicating that L2 speakers produced vowels with higher intensity than L1 speakers. Vowel Quality also had a significant

effect (Estimate = -1.97, SE = 0.28, $t = -7.01$, $p < .01$), with full vowels being produced more intensely than reduced vowels across both groups.

Importantly, the interaction between Language Group and Vowel Quality was significant (Estimate = 2.91, SE = 0.49, $t = 5.98$, $p < .01$), suggesting that the difference in intensity between full and reduced vowels varied depending on whether the speaker was a native or non-native English speaker. This implies that L2 speakers may exaggerate the intensity contrast between vowel types more than L1 speakers do. In general, the results demonstrate that both language background and vowel type significantly influence vocal intensity patterns in English vowel production.

4. Discussion

This study explored how vowel reduction functions as a correlate of word stress in native (L1) and non-native (L2) speakers of American English. In a word reading task using trisyllabic words, native speakers reduced vowels in unstressed positions more than L2 speakers, confirming the hypothesis that temporal vowel reduction is more prominent in L1 speech. While F0 pitch peaks did not differ significantly between groups, intensity emerged as a more reliable correlate: full vowels were produced with greater intensity than reduced vowels in both groups. These findings suggest that intensity, rather than pitch and spectral correlates, may play a more consistent role in signaling stress across both L1 and L2 productions. L2 speakers produced reduced vowels with broader spectral distributions, indicating less precise vowel reduction in the acoustic space. This likely reflects the influence of their native language, Brazilian Portuguese, which has a simpler vowel system than English. As a result, L2 speakers may merge reduced vowels into nearby full vowel categories, creating a mixed L1–L2 phonetic system [21, 22]. These findings support the idea that bilinguals can achieve functional phonological targets using non-native correlates, and that apparent similarities in stress assignment may disguise deeper acoustic differences between native and non-native speech [23, 24].

5. Conclusion

In sum, this study highlights the complex interplay of segmental and suprasegmental correlates in the assignment of word stress in American English and how these are variably realized by native and non-native speakers. Intensity emerged as a particularly consistent correlate across both L1 and L2 productions, with full vowels produced more intensely than reduced vowels. The poor reliance on vowel reduction and the broader spectral dispersion observed in L2 speakers suggest that Brazilian Portuguese speakers may approximately assign English stress patterns using alternative acoustic strategies shaped by their native phonological system.

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7. References

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